

Problems of School Management and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract:-This study investigated problems of school management and secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was employed in selecting a sample of 3616 students out of the population of 18, 078 students. "Problems of School Management Questionnaire (PSMQ)," and Senior Secondary Mathematics Achievement Test (SSMAT) were the instruments designed by the researcher, were used for data collection. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics; while the null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using population t-test and multiple regression analyses where applicable. Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet program was used in the analysis of data. Findings from the study revealed among others that; secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone is significantly high, disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation significantly influence secondary school students' academic performance respectively. Based on these results, conclusions were drawn and recommendations were made.

Keywords: Problems, Management, School Management, Secondary School, Students, Academic Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic requirement for effective school administration is inherent in the ability of the principal to positively influence teachers, students and other members in the society in the realization of educational goals. The role of the school manager (who is often referred to as the principal in Nigeria secondary school system) equally includes being able to translate educational policies into programmes and actions in the school. The success or failure of the school depends to a large extent in his ability and capacity to affect desired educational goals. Thus, his role as an executive head of the school is enormous and therefore brings a lot of challenges in terms of being able to manage not only instructional programmes but also teachers and students of the school to bring about positive change. In terms of specific duty of the principal, (Ocho, 2010) stressed that the principal's scope of work is "vast and intricate, and demands a lot of time, energy, dedication and sacrifice". He further outlined some of the

principal's pre-occupations to include the following; managing instructional programmes, staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resources management and school-community relationship management. In summary, the principal is seen as a setter of the tone of the school; an exemplar and above all a leader whose actions to a large degree determine the success of the school (Aja-Okorie, 2010). It can be added that, one of the ways through which one can assess a good secondary school administrator is through the academic performance of students.

Academic performance refers to the rate at which educational objectives are being achieved by those within the school system (Owan, 2012). Therefore, students' academic performance may be seen as the extent to which students are achieving educational goals and objectives. According to Erum and Zahoor (2011), students' academic performance and graduation rates have been the area of interest, and investigation of factors related to the academic performance of secondary students has been a topic of much interest to scholars. This may be because the school were established for the students, and their performance can be used to judge the entire school system effectiveness.

Within Calabar Education zone, secondary school students' academic performance seems to be poor, dwindling or unstable. Many students are struggling academically as revealed in their poor performance when they take some classroom or external examinations. This issue has raised the concern of parents, teachers, and policy makers, who have been questioning the effectiveness of the secondary school system not only within the zone, but also in Cross River State and Nigeria generally. In the past, secondary school students' poor academic performance was tied to poor supply of infrastructure, poor parental involvement, and students study habits among several other variables. However, with recent improvements in the raising and supply of buildings and other infrastructures by the Government, Non-Governmental organizations, and other interested parties, coupled with the improved involvement of parents in their children education, one expects to see a corresponding improvement in the academic performance of secondary school students. Where

this has not been clearly achieved, indicates that there are other problems within or outside the school system which may be contributing to such academic performance. On this note, the researcher considers problems associated with school management as having a link to secondary school students' academic performance.

Problems of school management refers to those impediments that hinders the effective design, control and smooth running of the school system towards achieving predetermined objectives. There are many factors responsible for the poor management of schools in Nigeria. These include: leadership styles, communication patterns, teachers' behaviour, infrastructural provision, adequacy of teachers, external supervision, and community interference. However, this study focused on three other critical areas of school management which include disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation.

Disciplinary control refers to the use of various techniques to ensure that the rules and regulations stated in an organization are respected and followed in order to facilitate the attainment of set goals (Owan, 2012). Discipline creates a good image of the school and prepares learners for the future. Disruptive behaviour amongst learners is eliminated if there is good discipline at school. The implementation of effective discipline at school is a key for the student in the journey to adulthood (Ehiane, 2014).

Classroom management refers to the orderly and professional arrangement and coordination of classroom activities in order to provide an environment conducive for teaching and learning (Owan, 2012). According to Ahmad, Hussain, Alia, Mubarka and Batool (2017), classroom management procedures assume an indispensable part in upgrading learners' learning. Classroom administration involves the exercises to arrange and guide classes to accomplish particular objectives. To keep up a positive learning condition in the classroom is instructor obligation. A very much oversight classroom offers a helpful domain for compelling instructing and learning.

Teachers' motivation refers to how teachers have a desire to perform better (Gitonga, 2012). According to Alarm and Farid (2011), motivation of teachers is very important as it affects the students directly. This fact is supported by Marques (2010) who concluded that motivation, satisfaction and performance are interdependent.

From the forgoing, it can be seen that there is need for improved students' academic performance within and outside the education zone. The reason is that, schools were established because of students and their performance is of high value to all stakeholders concerned. It is based on these issues that it was considered pertinent to investigate the problems of school management and how they influence secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone in Cross River State, Nigeria.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To achieve the goals of secondary education in Nigeria, there is need for increased academic performance of students in the secondary school system. In an ideal situation, efforts were supposed to be made by all those concerned to improve students' academic performance. The government were supposed to provide all the relevant materials and infrastructures, incentives and other services that will promote good academic performance of students. The school principals were expected to use their expertise and professionalism to make the school environment conducive for teachers and students in order boost their effectiveness and promote students' academic performance.

Unfortunately, the quality of students' academic performance especially in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State has been an issue of serious debate. Many students in the area doesn't seem to be performing well academically as indicated by their performance in internal and external examinations. Apart from poor performance in examinations, many secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone cannot read and write. As a result, they engage in serious examination malpractices as means to passing their examinations. This trend has not only affected the secondary school system, it has also eaten deep into the quality of graduates produced for the tertiary education level. Government had made efforts to send quality supervisors to schools for routine checks and inspection, they have improved their consistency in payment of teachers' salaries, more infrastructure and now in supply to schools and so on. Many parents are now actively involved in the training of their children through regular payment of fees, supervision at home, and in ensuring that students are not at home during school hours. All these new measures were lacking in time past, but with these efforts made by the government, teachers, and parents, to improve students' academic performance, there has not been any evident improvement in the performance of secondary school students within the education zone corresponding to the efforts made.

It is based on these lingering issues that has made the researcher to wonder whether problems school management such as disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation could be contributing to secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar education. The main problem of this study put in question form is; to what extent does problems of school management such as disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation influence secondary school students' academic performance? An attempt to investigate and provide an answer to this question necessitated the study.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The general purpose of this study was to investigate problems of school management and secondary school

students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Specifically, the study to investigate:

- i. the level of secondary students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone.
- ii. the influence of disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation on secondary students' academic performance.

IV. STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated in order to be tested in the course of the study.

- i. Secondary school academic performance in Calabar Education Zone is not significantly high.
- ii. Disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation has no significant influence on secondary students' academic performance.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

The relevant literatures that were related to this study were cited empirically in order to provide a better insight into what has been by earlier studies. The literatures were reviewed according to the sub-headings shown below.

5.1. *Disciplinary control and students' academic performance.*

Discipline is a vital ingredient for the success of students' academic performance. Students' performance but also scare others who develop phobia for boarding schools. Discipline at school plays a vital role in the achievement of expectations and goals. Disciplinary control and academic performances are the core of our today's education. Some scholars have attributed poor performance of students in academic to high level of indiscipline among students while others disagreed. Nevertheless, it becomes imperative in recent times that many schools have traded away discipline and as a result led to poor academic performance of students (Ehiane, 2014). According to Matsoga, (2003) in his study, he discovers the wide spread violence and misbehaviour that existed in many secondary schools. This lack of discipline which interferes with the teaching and learning process manifested itself in various ways including bullying, lateness, vandalism, alcohol consumption and substance abuse, truancy and inability or unwillingness to do class work at home.

Some studies empirically, have established a form of relationship between discipline and academic performance of students. For example, Ehiane (2014), established that there is a significant relationship between schools' discipline and students' academic performance. The study employed cross sectional research survey design in which questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection in addition to interview guide and document review. Simple percentage and Chi-square statistical method were used to analyse the data.

However, the findings of the study clearly recommended that effective school discipline should be encouraged in controlling students' behaviour, which will thus, affect students' general academic performance.

Nicholas, John and Eric (2016), carried out a study to determine the level of discipline and extent of impact of discipline on academic performance of pupils in public primary schools, among class eight pupils in the sub-county's public primary schools. The study adopted descriptive survey and correlational research designs. The study population comprised 2,450 class eight pupils in the sub-county's public primary schools. From 34 randomly selected schools, 817 pupils were selected by stratified random sampling. Results indicated that 46 (5.6%), 214 (26.2%), 413(50.6%) and 144 (17.6%) of the pupils had low, moderate, high, and very high discipline respectively. Also, discipline related positively with, and accounted for 23% of variance in the pupils' academic performance ($R = .480$, $\beta = .480$, $R^2 = .230$, $p < .05$). The study recommended enhancement of discipline among the pupils for improvement of their academic performance.

5.2. *Classroom management and students' academic performance.*

Classroom management procedures assume an indispensable part in upgrading learners' learning. Classroom administration involves the exercises to arrange and guide classes to accomplish particular objectives. To keep up a positive learning condition in the classroom is instructor obligation. A very much oversight classroom offers a helpful domain for compelling instructing and learning (Ahmad et. al., 2017). The five qualities of an effective classroom are security, open correspondence, common enjoying, shared objectives and connectedness (Zhang & Zhao, 2010). Classroom administration is a setup in which the educators build up and keep up conditions to empower learners to accomplish instructional destinations productively (Owan, 2012). Several studies have been conducted which established one form of relationship or the other, between classroom management and students' academic performance of students.

Igbinoba, and Aigbedion (2015), investigated the impact of classroom management techniques on students' academic performance in selected junior secondary schools in Municipal Area Council, to achieve this objective primary method of data collection was used and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) programme mean and simple percentages were used for analysis. The responses from the respondents through questionnaires were presented in tables and analysed. From the research results it is noticed that there is a significant difference between classroom management techniques in junior secondary schools in Municipal Area Council and there is a positive impact of classroom management techniques on students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Municipal Area Council.

In another study, Abisola, and Adam (2017), examined effective classroom management and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The survey design was adopted for the study. The population of 2044 Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students with a sample of 200 students selected from 5 public secondary schools in 4 clans within the study area

The result of their study revealed that, effective classroom management significantly influenced senior secondary one (SS1) students' academic performance; students in public secondary schools whose teachers gave instructions do differ significantly in terms of academic performance from those whose teachers do not; students in public schools whose teachers administer corporal punishment do differ significantly in terms of academic performance from other students whose teachers do not; instructional supervision significantly influence Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students' academic performance; and delegation of authority significantly influence Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students' academic performance.

5.3. Teachers' motivation and students' academic performance.

According to Marques (2010), motivation is what people need to perform better and can only work if the right person with the right skills has been placed in charge of the task at hand. Motivation covers all the reasons which cause a person to act including the negative ones like fear along with the more positive motives such as money, promotion or recognition (Aldair, 2009). The source of motivation is both intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation occurs when people engage in an activity without external incentives. They get motivated when they can control the amount of effort they put in an activity since they know the results they will get, will not be by luck. Extrinsic motivation has to do with incentives. Incentives are external to a person and are provided by the management in order to encourage workers to perform tasks (Owan, 2012). According to Alarm and Farid (2011), motivation of teachers is very important as it affects the students directly.

Onyambu (2014), carried out a study to examine the extent of the relationship between teachers' level of motivation and their students' performance in K.C.S.E examinations in Masimba Division of Masaba South District. The study's objectives were to: determine the level of teachers' motivation in secondary schools in Masimba Division and determine the relationship between teachers' level of motivation and the performance of students in K.C.S.E. The researcher adopted the survey research design. The population of this study was 200 secondary school teachers in 20 secondary schools in Masimba Division of Masaba South District. The researcher selected 80 teachers, representing 40% of the total population, using the stratified

sampling technique. The findings from this study revealed a significant relationship between teachers' motivation and students' academic performance.

Muhammad and Ibrahim (2014), investigated the impact of motivation on students' academic achievement in Kebbi state junior secondary schools' mathematics. An ex-post facto design was used in the study. The population consisted of 137,914 junior secondary school students in Kebbi state out of which 383 students were sampled. Two hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significant. Results were analysed using mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA. From the findings, results showed that gender difference were significant when impact of motivation on academic achievement was compared in male and female students. Also, other result indicates that there is significant difference in the academic achievement of highly motivated and lowly motivated students in mathematics. The study recommended among others that individual differences in ability, background and attitude must be taken into consideration.

5.4. Summary of Literature review

Several studies have been reviewed conceptually and empirically in the area of disciplinary control and classroom management and how they affect students' academic performance respectively. The review provided the researcher with more insights and knowledge about the topic. Some ideas were necessary to assist in designing the instruments of the study. The methodologies used by existing studies also provided a framework for the present study.

From the literatures reviewed, several gaps were identified. First, most of the studies conducted as cited herein were carried out in foreign countries. The results of these foreign studies might not be applicable to Nigeria, Cross River State, or Calabar South L.G.A. Secondly, only a handful of Nigerian studies were observed to have been conducted in relation to this present study, and none have examined the same variables as those of this study. There also seem to be no study in Cross River State and consequently in Calabar Education Zone that have examined problems of school management and the academic performance of secondary school students.

All these gaps identified above, makes this study different from all other existing studies. Given the need for improved students' academic performance which cannot be overemphasized, it is therefore, imperative that a study be conducted locally that will examine problems school management and the academic performance of students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. It is in filling these gaps identified above, that this study was undertaken with specific focus on disciplinary control and classroom management as factors.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study was ex-post facto research design. The population of the study comprised a total of 18, 078 students, (10, 119 males and 7959) females distributed across 81 public secondary schools in the zone. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used in selecting 20 per cent of the entire population resulting in a sample of 3, 616 students. The stratification was based on gender and location of the schools. Two instruments designed by the researcher were used for data collection. These include a questionnaire titled “Problems of School Management Questionnaire (PSMQ)” and Senior Secondary Mathematics Achievement Test (SSMAT). The PSMQ was made up of two parts, part1 and part 2. Part1 elicited information on respondent’s personal data. Part 2 of the instrument generated data on problems of school management, this was operationalized into: disciplinary control, classroom management and teachers’ motivation. All these variables of school management were measured using 10 items on a four-point modified Likert scale respectively. The SSMAT was designed with twenty objective test questions from senior secondary school mathematics and was used to measure students’ academic performance.

These instruments were validated by experts in test and measurement for face, content and construct validity. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through Cronbach

Alpha reliability method with a coefficient of .86 and .79 respectively from a pilot study conducted using two schools in Calabar Municipality that were not part of the sampled schools. These results confirmed that the instrument was reliable for use in obtaining the research objectives. The instruments were administered by the researcher with the help of some teachers in each school. Upon completion, the instruments were retrieved from the respondents for processing and data analysis. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics; while the null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using population t-test and multiple regression analyses where applicable. Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet program was used in the analysis of data.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.1. Presentation and interpretation of results

The results of this study were presented based on the hypothesis formulated earlier.

Hypothesis One (Ho₁)

Secondary school academic performance in Calabar Education Zone is not significantly high. The result of the analysis using Population t-test statistics is presented in table 1.

TABLE 1

Summary of population t-test result of secondary school students’ academic performance in Calabar in Education Zone.

n = 3616

Variable	Sample mean	μ	S ²	SE	t-cal.
Students’ academic performance	18.61	15	119.30	0.18	20.06*

* p < .05 df = 3615 t-crit. ∞ = 1.960 μ = hypothesized population mean

The results presented in Table 1, revealed that the calculated t-value of 20.06 is greater than the critical value of 1.960 meaning that, p < .05 at 3615 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis is rejected implying that, secondary school students’ academic performance in Calabar Education zone is significantly high.

Hypothesis Two (Ho₂)

Disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers’ motivation has no significant influence on secondary students’ academic performance. The results of the influence of disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers’ motivation on secondary students’ academic performance using multiple regression analysis is presented in table 2 below.

TABLE 2.

Summary of multiple regression results of the influence of disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers’ motivation on secondary students’ academic performance

n = 3616

Multiple R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE
0.075	0.006	0.005	10.90

The results presented in Table 9 revealed that; disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation, have a weak positive multiple correlation with secondary school students' academic performance ($R = .075$). This implies that the variables (disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation) to an extent, are quite relevant towards the determination of secondary school students' academic performance. These variables explained

0.6% of the total variance of secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone ($R^2 = .006$). By practical implication, the remaining 99.4% of the total variance, may have been due to other factors not studied presently. In determining whether the R^2 value of .006 obtained was statistically significant or not, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the regression analysis was presented as shown in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the Regression Analysis

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F	Sig. F
Regression	3	2437.35	812.45	6.84	0.0001*
Residual	3612	428837.4	118.73		
Total	3615	431274.8			

* Significant at $p < .05$

The results presented in Table 3 shows clearly that, the p -value .0001 obtained is less than .05 level of significance (i.e. $F = 6.84$; $p = .0001 < .05$). With this result, the null hypothesis is rejected implying that, disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation has significant influence on secondary students' academic performance. Hence, the R^2 value of .006 obtained, was

not due to chance. In order to determine the variable with the highest influence on secondary school students' academic performance, the relative contributions of the three variables (disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation) to secondary school students' academic performance was used as presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Relative contributions of disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation to secondary school teachers' job effectiveness.

Variables	Coefficients	SE	t Stat	p-value	Rank
Intercept	15.00	0.82	18.23	4.3E-71	–
Disciplinary control	0.06	0.02	2.82	0.005	1 st
Classroom management	0.04	0.02	2.05	0.040	3 rd
Teachers' motivation	0.05	0.02	2.64	0.008	2 nd

The results presented in table 4 revealed that, the three variables were statistically significant in influencing secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education. This is because their p -values were all less than the alpha level respectively. (i.e. p -values .005, .040, and .008 are all $< .05$). Out of the three variables studied, effective disciplinary control had the highest influence ($t = 2.82$); followed by teachers' motivation ($t = 2.64$); and then classroom management ($t = 2.05$) on secondary school students' academic performance.

7.2 Discussion of findings

The results of this study were discussed as follows:

7.2.1. Level of students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone

The findings of this study established that secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone is significantly high. This result does not imply that the

performance of secondary school students in the zone was near perfection, it simply revealed that their academic performance was above average.

7.2.2. Disciplinary control and students' academic performance

The finding of this study established a significant influence of disciplinary control on secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone. This finding agrees with Ehiane (2014), that earlier established that, there is a significant relationship between schools' discipline and students' academic performance. The findings of this present study also agree with the position held by the findings of Nicholas, John and Eric (2016), who carried out a study to determine the level of discipline and extent of its impact on academic performance of pupils in public primary schools, among class eight pupils in the sub-county's public primary schools. The results indicated that 46 (5.6%), 214 (26.2%), 413 (50.6%) and 144 (17.6%) of the pupils had

low, moderate, high, and very high discipline respectively. Also, discipline related positively with, and accounted for 23% of variance in the pupils' academic performance ($R = .480$, $\beta = .480$, $R^2 = .230$, $p < .05$). The study recommended enhancement of discipline among the pupils for improvement of their academic performance. Although their focus was on the primary school, there is a relationship between the results of their study and that of the present study because whatever affects primary school pupils' performance may sometimes affect secondary school students.

7.3.3. Classroom management and students' academic performance.

The finding of this study established a significant influence of classroom management on secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone. Igbinoba, and Aigbedion (2015), investigated the impact of classroom management techniques on students' academic performance in selected junior secondary schools in Municipal Area Council. The results of the study revealed among others that, there is a positive impact of classroom management techniques on students' academic performance in junior secondary schools in Municipal Area Council.

The finding of the present study also supports that position held by Abisola, and Adam (2017), that examined effective classroom management and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. The result of their study revealed that, effective classroom management significantly influenced senior secondary one (SS1) students' academic performance; students in public secondary schools whose teachers gave instructions do differ significantly in terms of academic performance from those whose teachers do not; students in public schools whose teachers administer corporal punishment do differ significantly in terms of academic performance from other students whose teachers do not; instructional supervision significantly influence Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students' academic performance; and delegation of authority significantly influence Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students' academic performance.

7.3.4. Teachers' motivation and students' academic performance.

The finding of this study established a significant influence of teachers' motivation on secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone. This finding is supported by the findings of Onyambu (2014), who examined the extent of the relationship between teachers' level of motivation and their students' performance in K.C.S.E examinations in Masimba Division of Masaba South District. The findings from this study revealed a significant relationship between teachers' motivation and students' academic performance. In another study, Muhammad and Ibrahim (2014), investigated the impact of motivation on students' academic achievement in Kebbi state junior secondary schools' mathematics. An ex-post facto design was

used in the study. The population consisted of 137,914 junior secondary school students in Kebbi state out of which 383 students were sampled. From the findings, it was revealed among others that, there is significant difference in the academic achievement of highly motivated and lowly motivated students in mathematics. The study recommended among others that individual differences in ability, background and attitude must be taken into consideration.

7.3.5. Combined influence of the three variables on secondary school students' academic performance.

This study established that, the three variables which includes disciplinary control, classroom management and teachers' motivation had a combined weak positive relationship that was statistically significant in predicting secondary school students' academic performance. When these three variables are jointly managed together, they influenced secondary school students' academic performance. However, out of the three variables, disciplinary control had the highest influence followed by teachers' motivation and then classroom management in that order on secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education Zone.

VIII. CONCLUSION

It was concluded through the findings of this study that; secondary school students' academic performance in Calabar Education zone is significantly high, disciplinary control, classroom management, and teachers' motivation significantly influence secondary school students' academic performance respectively. The three variables were jointly significant in influencing secondary school students' academic performance. Out of these three variables, disciplinary control had the highest influence on students' academic performance followed by teachers' motivation, and classroom management in that order.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

- i. The quality of education rendered within the education zone should be improved through regular supervision of teachers and consistent repairs, replacement, or supply of school facilities. This will help provide an enabling environment for effective teaching and learning to thrive.
- ii. Secondary school managers should ensure that, appropriate disciplinary measures and procedures are in place in order to bring to book, erring teachers. This will ensure that every teacher discharge his or her duties in accordance to set/expected standards.
- iii. Secondary school teachers should in the zone should be retrained on modern classroom management techniques that will enable them organize their classrooms, manage individual differences,

coordinate all the instructional duties for effective teaching and learning.

- iv. The government should ensure that teachers are adequately motivated through regular payment of salaries, promotion, allowances, and improved condition of service. Secondary school managers should ensure that intrinsic or extrinsic rewards such as praises or gifts are awarded to deserving teachers for their outstanding performance.

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